

Music Elements in Bhakthi Literature

*S. Sophia

Assistant professor & HOD i/c, Department of Music and Fine Arts, VISTAS.

**Corresponding author: S. Sophia*

Assistant professor & HOD i/c, Department of Music and Fine Arts, VISTAS.

Abstract

Bhakthi Literature is a substantial part of Indian culture, spirituality transpired during medieval period comprising devotional texts written in various languages by poets and saints. The bhakthi literature includes various forms like poems, songs, bhajans, keerthanais, padams created by saints and poets from divergent backgrounds. Bhakthi literature accentuates personal and emotional bond between God and devotees. Bhakthi literature stimulated various art forms such as music, dance, painting and influenced philosophical traditions such as Advaita and Vedanta which highlight oneness of all beings.

Keywords: *Music, Bhakthi, literature, Bhajans, Keerthanai, Padams, Devotion.*

Music in Worship:

Music is an important part of hymns of praise to God. Music of hymns is an important part of worship. Devotional literature is mostly sung in musical form. Traditional hymns are often used to express faith also the practice of worshipping god through music is found in devotional literature.

Types of devotional literature:

Bhakti literature is associated with Venpa, kalippa, Naanmanimalai, Virutham, pathigam, Anthathi, Ula, Pallu, Pillaitamizh, kuravanji folk song tradition and musical tradition.

Specialties of Bhakti Literature:

The highlights of devotional literature are intense emotional appeal, simplicity, eloquence, sweet music and accessibility, promoting religious harmony and social equality through languages and accessible poetic forms.

Origin of Bhakti Literature:

Bhakti literature has its origins in the Tholkapiyam, the "Poovai Nilai, "Puranilai vaazhthu, " Kadavul Vaazhthodu Kanniya Varume " Also Bhakti literature has been supported by Thirumurukattupadai and Silapathikaram. The worship of Arugan by the Kavunthiadigal and the worship of Mayavan (krishna) by the Aaichiyars (Yaadhavas) may be the origin of the Patthima (Bhakthima) tradition. It is said that the Tamil devotional literature is so special because the inner traditions of Sangham literature have been adapted to Bhakti literature. Sangam literature is spiritualistic and has the highest goal of civilization and love. The development of devotional literature is said to have developed the imagination of devotional songs due to the narratives provided by Puranic stories, northern language legends and hearsay. It is said that the oral tradition and the tradition of singing with music added sweetness to the Tamil hymns.

Musical Elements in Bhakti Literature:

Starting with Karaikal Ammaiyar, Cheraman Perumal, Panniru Azhwars, Thevara Moovar, many devotional processions were played in the 7th, 8th, and 9th centuries. Jain, Buddhist devotional songs also proliferated. And also Saiva, Vaishnavism chants sound echoed and multiplied. The Twelve Thirumurai and the Four Thousand Divyaprabandhams are partial arks. Following the Nayanmars, Azhwars, Arunagirinathar, Pattinathar, Thayumanavar, Vallalar, and the hymns of Islamic and Christian music limit has been reached unparalleled.

Bhakti Ilakkiyam Authors and Poems:

S.No	Author	Poem
1	Tholkaapiyar	Tholkaapiyam
2	Thirunyanasambhandhar	Thirukkadaikkaapu
3	Thirunaavukkarasar	Thevaram
4	Sundharamurthy Naayanmaar	Thiruppaatu
5	Maanickavasagar	Thiruvagasam
6	Thirumoolar	Thirumanthiram
7	Sekkizhar	Periya puranam
8	Abhirami bhattar	Abhirami Anthathi
9	Poigai Azhwar	Mudhal Thiruvanthahi
10	Boothathazhwar	Irاندam Thirumozhi
11	Peyazhwar	Moondram Thiruvanthathi
12	Thirumazhisai Azhwar	Naanmugan Thiruvanthathi
		Thiru chantha virutham
13	Nammazhwar	Thiruvaimozhi, Thiruvirutham,
		Periya Thirumozhi,
		Thiruvasiriyam
14	MadhurakaviAzhwar	Kanninunsiruthambinal
15	Kulasekara Azhwar	Perumal Thirumozhi
16	Periyazhwar	Thirupallandu, Periyazhwar Thirumozhi
17	Aandal	Thiruppavai NaachiyarThirumozhi
18	Thondaradipodi azhwar	Thirumaalai, Thirupalliyezhuchi
		Amalanathipiran
19	Thiruppavai azhwar	Periya Thirumozhi, Thiruvezhukootrarikkai
		PeriyaThirumadal
		Siriya Thirumadal
20	Thirumangai azhwar	Thirukurunthandagam
		Thirunedunthandagam
21	Kaaraikal Ammaiyaar	Thiruvaalangadu Mootha Thirupathigam
22	Guru Nyanasambhandhar	Sokkanatha venpaa
23	Kumaraguruparar	Meeenakshiamman pillaitamizh
24	Thirukoodarasappa kavirayar	Kutraala kuravanji

Conclusion:

Bhakti literature has a unique place in Tamil literature and it has made a great contribution to the Tamil language, literature, music and dance. Tamil Bhakti literature flourished due to bhakti movement emphasized direct and personal contact with god. Adi shankarar, Ramanujar, chaithanya, Mirabai were the prominent saints of the bhakti movement. Tamil literature has had a profound impact on the spiritual life and culture of the people. The Bhakti movement began composing devotional songs and poems in the language of the common people. Bhakti movement broke down social inequalities and opened the way to spiritual salvation for all.

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